

STAGED SURGICAL MANAGEMENT IN ACUTE SUPPURATIVE CHOLANGITIS

Managementul chirurgical etapizat în angiolocolita acută purulentă

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Ion COTONEȚ

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2637-4671>

PhD student, Department of Surgery No. 2, “Nicolae Testemițanu”

University of Medicine and Pharmacy

E-mail: cotonet.ion@gmail.com

Alexandru FERDOHLEB

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3290-8139>

PhD hab. in Medical Sciences, Associate Professor, Department of Surgery No. 2,

“Nicolae Testemițanu” State Medical University

E-mail: alexandru.ferdohleb@usmf.md

Adrian HOTINEANU

<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-8791-0810>

PhD hab. in Medical Sciences, Professor, Head of Department, Department of Surgery No. 2, University of Medical Sciences “Nicolae Testemițanu”

E-mail: adrian.hotineanu@usmf.md

Ivan CUCU

<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-1086-8746>

scientific researcher, Laboratory of Reconstructive Surgery of the Digestive Tract, INCMS, USMF “Nicolae Testemițanu”

E-mail: ivan.cucu@usmf.md

Summary. Acute suppurative cholangitis is a severe biliary tract complication requiring urgent intervention. This retrospective study analyzed 345 patients managed between 2014 and 2024 at Surgery Clinic No. 2, stratified according to Tokyo 2018 Guidelines. Initial minimally invasive decompression, mainly endoscopic, was followed by definitive surgery to restore bilio-enteric flow. Endoscopic decompression was achieved in 328 patients (95%), percutaneous transhepatic drainage in 8 (2.3%), and sequential ERCP with stenting and lavage in 36 severe cases (10.3%). Nasobiliary drainage was used in 8 patients (2.3%). Minimally invasive procedures were effective in 260 cases (75.4%), allowing laparoscopic cholecystectomy, while 85 cases (24.6%) required Roux-en-Y derivations. Postoperative mortality was 4.9% (17 patients), linked to severe, refractory forms. Staged management with urgent minimally invasive decompression proved efficient in controlling biliary infection, reducing emergency surgery, and lowering mortality.

Key words: acute cholangitis, staged treatment, ERCP, biliary drainage

Introduction

Acute suppurative cholangitis represents one of the most dramatic emergencies in biliary surgery, resulting from the association of mechanical obstruction of the biliary tree with severe infection and systemic septic syndrome. Epidemiological data indicate that the

incidence of this entity is rising, driven by the high prevalence of choledocholithiasis and the increasing occurrence of benign and malignant biliary strictures¹. In the absence of effective biliary drainage, mortality rates may exceed 50%, underscoring the vital importance of prompt diagnosis and early initiation of treatment².

Over the past decades, therapeutic management has undergone a paradigm shift. Whereas in the past the standard treatment relied on emergency surgical interventions – with high mortality among hemodynamically unstable patients – current practice has shifted toward minimally invasive techniques, both endoscopic and percutaneous, which enable rapid decompression of the biliary system, followed by definitive surgery at an optimized moment³. This transition has been made possible by advances in therapeutic endoscopy, interventional radiology, and modern anesthesiology, which together have supported the development of a staged and individualized treatment algorithm.

A fundamental milestone in standardizing international practice has been the Tokyo Guidelines 2018, which introduced standardized criteria for diagnosis, severity stratification, and therapeutic decision-making⁴. According to these recommendations, early biliary drainage – preferably using minimally invasive approaches – constitutes the cornerstone of treatment, followed by definitive surgical intervention tailored to the etiology and the patient's general condition.

The staged surgical strategy, based on the principle of urgent biliary decompression, offers several well-demonstrated advantages: reduction in the incidence of septic shock, rapid stabilization of the patient, avoidance of major emergency surgical procedures in critical settings, and decreased perioperative mortality. The specialized literature confirms that ERCP with sphincterotomy and stent placement is the method of choice, while in refractory cases, percutaneous transhepatic drainage or biliodigestive derivations remain valid salvage options⁵.

In this context, the present study aims to evaluate our clinical experience in the staged surgical management of acute suppurative cholangitis, analyzing clinical outcomes and the impact of integrating minimally invasive methods with definitive surgery, in accordance with modern principles established by international guidelines.

Materials and methods

This retrospective study included 345 patients diagnosed with acute suppurative cholangitis, hospitalized and treated at Surgery Clinic No. 2, Nicolae Testemițanu State University of Medicine and Pharmacy, between 2014 and 2024. The diagnosis was established based on clinical, laboratory, and imaging criteria, and severity was assessed according

¹ Lavillegrand, Jean-Rémi, et al. Acute cholangitis in intensive care units: clinical, biological, microbiological spectrum and risk factors for mortality: a multicenter study, in: *Critical Care* 25.1 (2021): 49.

² Lyu, Yunxiao, et al. Impact of the timing of endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography for the treatment of acute cholangitis: a meta-analysis and systematic review, in: *Surgical Laparoscopy Endoscopy & Percutaneous Techniques* 32.6 (2022): 764-769.

³ Liao, Yi-Jun, et al. Critically-Ill patients with biliary obstruction and cholangitis: bedside fluoroscopic-free endoscopic drainage versus percutaneous drainage, in: *Journal of Clinical Medicine* 11.7 (2022): 1869.

⁴ Kiriya, Seiki, et al. Tokyo Guidelines 2018: diagnostic criteria and severity grading of acute cholangitis (with videos), in: *Journal of Hepato-Biliary-Pancreatic Sciences* 25.1 (2018): 17-30.

⁵ Aouroud, H., et al. Urgent ERCP reduces mortality in acute cholangitis due to common bile duct stones, in: *Endoscopy* 56.S 02 (2024): eP024.

to the Tokyo Guidelines 2018⁶, which classify the disease into mild (Grade I), moderate (Grade II), and severe (Grade III) forms.

Therapeutic management was correlated with the severity grade and was carried out in a staged manner. In the first stage, the primary objective was biliary decompression by minimally invasive methods, with the majority of patients undergoing endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) with sphincterotomy, stenting, and, in selected cases, nasobiliary drainage. When endoscopic access was not feasible or had failed, ultrasound-guided percutaneous transhepatic biliary drainage (PTBD) was performed.

After patient stabilization and resolution of septic manifestations, the second stage of treatment consisted of definitive surgical interventions. These included laparoscopic cholecystectomy in patients with associated gallbladder lithiasis and Roux-en-Y biliodigestive derivations in patients with biliary strictures or in cases requiring the restoration of a stable bilioenteric flow.

Data analysis focused on the type and timing of drainage procedures, the success rate of decompression, the distribution of definitive surgical interventions, and postoperative mortality, in correlation with disease severity. The results were compared between groups to highlight the effectiveness of the staged surgical strategy and the role of minimally invasive methods in optimizing outcomes for patients with acute suppurative cholangitis.

Results

The analysis of the 345 patients included in the study allowed for a detailed evaluation of the effectiveness of the staged surgical strategy applied in acute suppurative cholangitis. The mean age of patients was 64.2 ± 11.8 years, with a relatively balanced sex distribution – 178 women (51.6%) and 167 men (48.4%).

In the initial stage, biliary decompression was the primary objective and was predominantly achieved through endoscopic methods. Endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) was performed in 328 patients (95%), confirming the central role of this procedure in the current therapeutic algorithm, particularly in moderate (Grade II TG18) and severe (Grade III TG18) forms⁷. Within this group, 36 patients (10.3%) required sequential sessions with successive stent placement and intraductal lavage, especially in severe cases (Grade III TG18) with complex obstruction and infection refractory to initial drainage.

Nasobiliary drainage was used in 8 patients (2.3%) as an adjunct method for continuous evacuation and monitoring of biliary secretions. In situations where endoscopic access was impossible or unsuccessful (8 cases, 2.3%), ultrasound-guided percutaneous transhepatic biliary drainage (PTBD) was performed, allowing for effective decompression and stabilization of critically ill patients⁸ (Grade III TG18).

The second stage of treatment was implemented after sepsis control and improvement of biological status. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy was performed in 260 patients (75.4%), constituting the standard definitive treatment for associated gallbladder lithiasis (predomi-

⁶ Kiriya, Seiki, et al. Tokyo Guidelines 2018: diagnostic criteria and severity grading of acute cholangitis (with videos), in: *Journal of Hepato-Biliary-Pancreatic Sciences* 25.1 (2018): 17-30.

⁷ Tan, Ming, Ove B. Schaffalitzky de Muckadell, and Stig B. Laursen. Association between early ERCP and mortality in patients with acute cholangitis, in: *Gastrointestinal endoscopy* 87.1 (2018): 185-192; Iqbal, Umair, et al. Emergent versus urgent ERCP in acute cholangitis: a systematic review and meta-analysis, in: *Gastrointestinal endoscopy* 91.4 (2020): 753-760.

⁸ Gupta, Pankaj, et al. Percutaneous transhepatic biliary drainage in patients at higher risk for adverse events: experience from a tertiary care referral center, in: *Abdominal Radiology* 45.8 (2020): 2547-2553.

nantly Grade I–II TG18). In 85 cases (24.6%), particularly in patients with biliary strictures or complex reconstructive indications, Roux-en-Y biliodigestive derivations were carried out to ensure an adequate and durable bilioenteric flow.

Overall postoperative mortality was 4.9% (17 patients), occurring exclusively in patients with severe forms (Grade III TG18) refractory to minimally invasive treatment, which highlights both the particular severity of this category and the limitations of staged therapy in the face of advanced sepsis⁹.

This analysis demonstrates that early application of minimally invasive biliary drainage enabled clinical stabilization in the majority of cases and created optimal conditions for definitive surgical treatment. The results emphasize the effectiveness of the staged approach, while also underlining that refractory severe cases remain associated with a significant vital risk, even in the context of the most modern therapeutic methods.

Conclusions

The staged surgical strategy, based on early application of minimally invasive biliary decompression, proved essential for the prompt control of biliary infection and the prevention of septic complications. Patient stabilization through ERCP or, when this was not feasible, through percutaneous transhepatic drainage enabled subsequent definitive interventions to be performed safely, either as laparoscopic cholecystectomy or as biliodigestive derivations tailored to complex cases. The mortality rate of 4.9%, limited to patients with refractory severe forms, aligns with values reported in the international literature and confirms the decisive role of early drainage¹⁰.

These findings support the hypothesis that a staged therapeutic approach optimizes the prognosis of patients with acute suppurative cholangitis, in accordance with the recommendations of the Tokyo Guidelines 2018⁴ and the results of recent multicenter studies¹¹.

⁹ Hedjoudje, Abdellah, et al. Outcomes and predictors of delayed endoscopic biliary drainage for severe acute cholangitis due to choledocholithiasis in an intensive care unit, in: *Digestive and Liver Disease* 55.6 (2023): 763-770.

¹⁰ Hedjoudje, Abdellah, et al. Outcomes and predictors of delayed endoscopic biliary drainage for severe acute cholangitis due to choledocholithiasis in an intensive care unit, in: *Digestive and Liver Disease* 55.6 (2023): 763-770; Schneider, Jochen, et al. Mortality Risk for Acute Cholangitis (MAC): a risk prediction model for in-hospital mortality in patients with acute cholangitis, in: *BMC gastroenterology* 16.1 (2016): 15.

¹¹ Tan, Ming, Ove B. Schaffalitzky de Muckadell, and Stig B. Laursen. Association between early ERCP and mortality in patients with acute cholangitis, in: *Gastrointestinal endoscopy* 87.1 (2018): 185-192; Iqbal, Umair, et al. Emergent versus urgent ERCP in acute cholangitis: a systematic review and meta-analysis, in: *Gastrointestinal endoscopy* 91.4 (2020): 753-760; Schwed, Alexander C., et al. Association of admission laboratory values and the timing of endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography with clinical outcomes in acute cholangitis, in: *JAMA surgery* 151.11 (2016): 1039-1045.